

Research Article

Tuning of magnetic properties and giant magnetoimpedance effect in multilayered microwires

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ABSTRACT

We studied the magnetic properties and Giant Magnetoimpedance (GMI) effect in amorphous Co-rich microwires with similar chemical compositions and different diameters with magnetic (Co, Permalloy) and non-magnetic (Cu) layers deposited by magnetic sputtering onto glass-coating. Studies of magnetic properties and GMI effect of as-prepared microwires and the same microwires with deposited magnetic and non-magnetic layers reveal substantial impact of such layers on GMI effect and hysteresis loops. Both as-prepared samples present soft magnetic properties and high GMI effect. The contribution of magnetic layers is observed in hysteresis loop at higher magnetic field, with hysteresis loops similar to those observed in microwires with mixed amorphous-crystalline structure. Meanwhile, both magnetic and non-magnetic layers affect low field hysteresis loops of both samples. Additionally, the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, and magnetic field dependences of GMI ratio are substantially affected by the presence of magnetic and non-magnetic layers deposited onto glass-coating. We discussed the observed experimental dependences considering both change of the internal stresses originated by the sputtered layer as well as the magnetostatic interaction between the amorphous ferromagnetic nucleus and deposited magnetic layers.

1. Introduction

Studies of amorphous magnetic materials have attracted continuous attention for several decades due to their excellent soft magnetic properties combined with superior mechanical and corrosion properties [1–5]. The distinctive domain structure of amorphous magnetic wires with cylindrical symmetry enables a number of properties such as the giant magnetoimpedance (GMI) effect or magnetic bistability, suitable for several technological applications including magnetic and magnetoelastic sensors, smart composite materials or electronic surveillance [6–10].

The domain structure of amorphous wires is commonly described in terms of a core-shell model [10–14]. According to this model (theoretically predicted and experimentally observed in several publications), the domain structure is described as consisting of an inner axially

magnetized single-domain surrounded by an external domain shell [10–14]. Cylindrical symmetry, together with magnetoelastic anisotropy, plays a determining role in the inner single domain diameter and the distribution of magnetization in the outer shell [8–14].

A large change in the impedance Z of a magnetic conductor under the influence of an external magnetic field refers the aforementioned GMI effect [6,7]. The GMI effect is usually explained in terms of classical electrodynamics by a change in the thickness of the skin layer, δ , of a magnetic conductor with high magnetic permeability under the influence of an applied magnetic field, H [6,7]. For the case of magnetic wires, the dependence $\delta(H)$ is determined by the magnetic field dependence of circumferential magnetic permeability, μ_ϕ , given by Refs. [6,7]:

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$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi\sigma\mu_0\mu_\phi f}} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity, μ_0 - the permeability of vacuum and f is the frequency of the AC current.

The magnetic field dependence of Z , typically represented through the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, is usually the most common parameter for characterization of the GMI effect [6,7]. Such GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, is defined as [6,7].

$$\Delta Z/Z = [Z(H) - Z(H_{max})]/Z(H_{max}) \bullet 100 \quad (2)$$

being H_{max} the maximum applied DC magnetic field (typically about a few kA/m).

It must be clarified that $\Delta Z/Z$ -values are substantially affected by several parameters: frequency, f , of AC current, AC current amplitude, H_{max} -value, applied and internal stress, magnetic anisotropy of studied material, etc. [7,15–18]. Thus, for relatively low frequencies (generally at $f < 1$ MHz), contributions from domain wall motion and magnetization rotation are effective [7,19]. However, at higher frequencies ($f > 10$ MHz), the domain wall motion is strongly damped by eddy currents and the magnetization rotation dominates the GMI effect [7]. Additionally, the magnetic field dependence of GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ is influenced by the type of magnetic anisotropy of the magnetic wire. In particular, a double -peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependency is typically observed for magnetic wires presenting circumferential magnetic anisotropy, whereas a single maximum of $\Delta Z/Z$ at $H=0$ is reported for magnetic wires with axial magnetic anisotropy [6,16]. In addition, it has been predicted and even experimentally shown that a decrease in diameter is associated with an increase in the resonant frequency and, consequently, with an increase in the optimal frequency range of the GMI effect [15]. Consequently, for each magnetic wire with given geometrical parameters and magnetic anisotropy type (wire diameter and chemical composition), there is an optimal frequency, f_o , at which the highest GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z_m$, is observed [3].

Typically, the highest $\Delta Z/Z$ -values ($\Delta Z/Z_m$ near 200–300%) are observed in Co-rich magnetic wires with vanishing magnetostriction coefficients, λ_s [6,7]. Such $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values can be further optimized by either careful selection of the magnetic wire chemical composition (with vanishing λ_s and internal stresses) or by appropriate post-processing. Following these approaches, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values up to or slightly above 700% have been recently achieved [18,20].

The achieved high $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values allow to obtain excellent (up to 10%/A/m) magnetic field sensitivity, η , expressed as [7,20]:

$$\eta = \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\Delta Z}{Z} \right)}{\partial H} \quad (3)$$

Accordingly, magnetic wires with high $\Delta Z/Z_m$ and η -values have been employed for the development of extremely sensitive magnetometers and magnetic field sensors with pico-Tesla magnetic field sensitivity, suitable for monitoring low magnetic fields [21,22].

Hence, it is evident that the performance of sensors and devices based on the GMI effect can be significantly improved by using materials with a higher GMI effect. Additionally, presently achieved $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are still fairly lower than the theoretically predicted $\Delta Z/Z \approx 3000\%$ [23]. Accordingly, a substantial attention is presently paid to the tailoring of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies through the modification of the magnetic anisotropy of the magnetic materials [3,18,20].

As a general rule, the magnetic anisotropy of amorphous wires correlates with the magnetostriction coefficient (determined mainly by the chemical composition of the alloy) or by annealing (including stress or magnetic field or annealing) [3,20]. However, an alternative approach allowing to tune the magnetic anisotropy of magnetic wires consists of depositing of magnetic and non-magnetic layers onto the glass-coating [24]. Up to the moment, Vazquez et al. [24,25], Kraus et al. [26], and

Chiriac et al. [27] have been the pioneers of this method, the former using electrodeposition and the latter by sputtering. This approach allows to tailor the magnetic properties of such multilayered microwires by selecting the chemical composition of the amorphous metallic nucleus, the thickness and chemical composition of the layers, which induce the mechanical stresses associated with such a layer. This line of action has also been applied to other related systems different from glass-coated microwires, as, e.g., a non-magnetic conductive wire with a Fe–Ni–Co magnetic layer [28] or CoFeMoSiB ribbons with a Fe layer on top [29].

Accordingly, the purpose of this paper is to study the GMI effect and magnetic properties of amorphous Co-rich microwires by magnetic or non-magnetic layers with different thicknesses deposited onto glass-coating by sputtering.

2. Experimental

We studied the influence of magnetic (Co and Permalloy) or non-magnetic (Cu) layers up to 600 nm thick deposited on a glass coating of $\text{Co}_{67}\text{Fe}_{3.85}\text{Ni}_{1.45}\text{B}_{11.5}\text{Si}_{14.5}\text{Mo}_{1.7}$ (hereinafter referred to as sample 1 with metallic nucleus diameter $d = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$ and total diameter $D = 11.9 \mu\text{m}$) and $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{1.5}\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ (hereinafter sample 2 with $d = 19.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $D = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$) glass-coated microwire on the magnetic properties and GMI effect. The images of the samples (obtained using Zeiss Gemini 500 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope) are provided in Fig. 1.

Both studied microwires have been prepared using the so-called Taylor-Ulitovsky preparation method involving rapid solidification of previously melted metallic alloy inside the glass capillary [8,30,31]. Such a capillary formed from softened glass, with an alloy previously melted by a high-frequency inductor, is quenched by a cooling liquid jet, and then captured by a rotating receiving spool [8,30,31].

The hysteresis loops were evaluated using a fluxmetric method developed for characterization of soft magnetic microwires and described elsewhere [32]. In this method, the studied microwires were magnetized in the axial direction by a thin (8 mm in diameter) 120 mm long solenoid, creating a uniform magnetic field H . For a better comparison of the studied samples, the hysteresis loops were presented as the dependence of the normalized magnetization M/M_o on H (where M is the magnetic moment at given H and M_o is the magnetic moment of the samples at the maximum employed magnetic field amplitude).

The sample impedance, Z , was obtained from the reflection coefficient S_{11} measured using a vector network analyzer. The $\Delta Z/Z$ values and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies were estimated using eq. (2) from the $Z(H)$ dependencies measured up to $H_{max} = 18$ kA/m. The use of a specially designed microstrip sample holder allowed us to evaluate the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies up to GHz frequencies, f [33]. The selected 6 mm long microwires were placed into the sample holder and soldered to a transmission line structure. One wire end was connected to the inner conductor of a coaxial line through a matched microstrip line, while the other was connected to the ground plane.

The amorphous structure of studied microwires has been confirmed X-ray diffraction (XRD) performed by a BRUKER (D8 Advance) X-ray diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. A broad halo typical for completely amorphous materials was observed for both studied microwires (see Fig. 2).

The magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , of both studied microwires was evaluated using the so-called small angle magnetization rotation (SAMR) method, described in detail elsewhere [34]. Such technique was recently successfully adapted for λ_s evaluation in glass-coated microwires of reduced diameter [35]. Using that experimental setup, we obtained λ_s -values of $-3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $-1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for samples 1 and 2 respectively.

Thin films of Cobalt (Co), Permalloy (Py) and copper (Cu) were deposited by RF magnetron sputtering onto the glass coating of both microwires. The power of the magnetron source was kept constant (100

Fig. 1. SEM images of the sample 1 (a) and sample 2 (b) with deposited layer of 600 nm.

Fig. 2. XRD spectra of studied samples.

W) for all the materials. The microwires were placed in a sample holder where the microwires were fixed from their two extremes. The geometry of the sample holder and the deposition system allowed the continuous rotation of the sample holder (at 14 r.p.m.), which permitted a

homogenous deposition on all the surface of the microwire (excepting the fixed extremes).

The thicknesses of the thin films were 300 and 600 nm. The rate of deposition of each material was determined from x ray reflectometry measurements from thin films deposited over glass substrates in the same sample holder and in the same conditions (magnetron power, distance, rotation speed). Hence, the thickness of the films over the microwires was controlled by adjusting the deposition time according to the deposition rate.

3. Results and discussion

The hysteresis loops of both studied samples prior depositing of magnetic (Co and Permalloy) or non-magnetic (Cu) layers are provided in Fig. 3. As expected from the low negative λ_s -values, rather soft magnetic properties (coercivities, H_c , about 40 and 22 A/m for samples 1 and 2 respectively) are evidenced from the hysteresis loops.

The contribution of magnetic Co layer on hysteresis loops of both studied samples is shown in Fig. 4a and b. The presence of hysteresis observed up to rather high magnetic field must be attributed to contribution of magnetically harder Co layer. Such contribution is more evident in the sample 1 (see Fig. 4a). Relatively higher contribution of the magnetic Co layer visible in sample 1 must be attributed to lower volume of amorphous metallic nucleus in this sample with metallic nucleus diameter $d = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$. In sample 2 with larger d , the contribution

Fig. 3. Hysteresis loop of as-prepared samples 1 (a) and sample 2 (b).

Fig. 4. Hysteresis loop of sample 1 (a) and sample 2 (b) with Co-layer of 600 nm thickness.

of the magnetic Co layer is less noticeable (see Fig. 4b).

Similarly, the contribution of the magnetic Permalloy layer can be easily assessed from the hysteresis loop of sample 1 with the deposited 600 nm thick Permalloy layer (see Fig. 5a). The difference between the hysteresis loops of the sample 1 with the deposited 600 nm thick Permalloy layer and the same sample 1 with the deposited 600 nm thick Co layer is that the contribution of Co-layer is observed up to about 150 kA/m (see Fig. 4a). Meanwhile, the Permalloy layer contribution is observed up to only about 10 kA/m (see Fig. 5a). Therefore, in contrast to the sample 1 with Permalloy layer, the contribution of Co-layer is relevant for $H > 10$ kA/m (see Fig. 5b).

This difference must be attributed to the softer magnetic properties of the Permalloy layer.

To assess the influence of coatings on the GMI effect, it may be of interest to analyze hysteresis loops measured in low magnetic field region. Such hysteresis loops are provided in Figs. 6 and 7 for the samples 1 and 2 respectively.

As can be observed, low field region of hysteresis loops of studied samples is substantially influenced by the presence of magnetic and non-magnetic layers. Generally, the presence of non-magnetic (Cu) layers is reflected by a more rectangular hysteresis loop shape in both studied samples (see Figs. 6a and 7a). As the thickness of the Cu layer increases, the squareness ratio, M_r/M_o , increases (see Figs. 6a and 7a).

This was also observed by Pirota et al. [36] with relatively thin (30 or 100 nm) coating with non-magnetic metals (Au, Ti) on top of a

Fig. 5. Hysteresis loop of sample 1 (a) and sample 2 (b) with Co-layer of 600 nm thickness.

microwire with a CoFe-based core alloy. On the other hand, when a thick (several microns) Cu coating was electrodeposited, the effect was the opposite, favoring a transverse anisotropy. Nevertheless, they did not study the intermediate range that we are exploring, although our results are quite similar to their case with quite thin films.

However, in the case of magnetic (Co or Permalloy) layers, the M_r/M_o -ratio grows slower: for the same coating thickness, M_r/M_o -ratio is lower in the case of both samples (see Fig. 6b, c, 7b, 7c).

As expected from the aforementioned experimental results, the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are substantially affected by the presence of the additional layer. Thus, generally lower $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are observed for sample 1 when any (magnetic or non-magnetic) layer is deposited (see Fig. 8a-d).

Thickness of both magnetic and non-magnetic layers is another parameter that affects $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies. As shown in Fig. 9, although $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values of the sample 1 with Co-layers of different thickness (300 nm and 600 nm) are almost the same, the evolution of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies with frequency are rather different. Thus, in the sample 1 with 300 nm thick Co-layer the highest $\Delta Z/Z_m$ is observed at $f = 50$ MHz, whereas in the sample 1 with 600 nm thick Co-layer the highest $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value is observed at $f = 80$ MHz.

Meanwhile, higher $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are observed in sample 1 with 600 nm thick Cu-layer (see Fig. 10a and b).

The opposite tendency is observed in sample 2, where an increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values is observed when any (magnetic or non-magnetic) layer is deposited (see Fig. 11a-d).

Similarly to the sample 1, the thickness of magnetic and non-magnetic layers affects the $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies

Fig. 6. Hysteresis loops of sample 1 with deposited non-magnetic Cu-layer with thickness of 300 and 600 nm (a) Co-layer with thickness of 300 and 600 nm (b) and Permalloy layer with thickness 600 nm (c).

of the sample 2. Thus, with an increase in the Co layer thickness from 300 nm to 600 nm, an increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values is observed (see Fig. 12). Remarkably higher $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are obtained in the sample with the 600 nm thick Co layer (see Fig. 12). Additionally, the evolution of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies with frequency is affected by the Co layer thickness.

The influence of thickness of non-magnetic Cu layer in the sample 2 is shown in Fig. 13. In this case, an increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values is observed. The frequency $\Delta Z/Z_m$ dependence is also affected by the Cu layer thickness.

Similarly to sample 2 covered by Co layer, a remarkable increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values is observed in the sample 2 covered with 600 nm thick Permalloy layer (see Fig. 14).

The frequency dependencies of $\Delta Z/Z_m$ for the samples 1 and 2 are summarized in Fig. 15. As can be observed from Fig. 15, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are substantially improved in the sample 2 and $\Delta Z/Z_m$ (f) is affected by the magnetic and non-magnetic layers in both samples.

Fig. 7. Hysteresis loops of sample 2 with deposited non-magnetic Cu-layer with thickness of 300 and 600 nm (a) Co-layer with thickness of 300 and 600 nm (b) and Permalloy layer with thickness 600 nm (c).

Obviously, the magnetic field sensitivity, η , given by (3) is one of the important parameters for the GMI materials performance. From the relationship between η and $\partial\left(\frac{\Delta Z}{Z}\right)$, given by (3), it follows that the higher $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values, the higher the η -values. Therefore, performed comparison of the $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values and their frequency dependence is meaningful for the GMI effect performance of studied samples.

The comparison of the effect of deposited layers on GMI ratio of studied samples is resumed in Table 1, where $\Delta Z/Z_m$ and f_0 -values are provided.

For better understanding the obtained experimental results, we must consider two types of effects. Thus, both magnetic and non-magnetic layers deposited on the glass-coating affect the internal stresses distribution inside the metallic nucleus arising during the glass-coated microwires preparation. The origin of the internal stresses in glass-coated microwires is commonly discussed in terms of three different contributions consisting of different thermal expansion coefficients of the metallic alloy and glass, quenching process, and drawing [3,30,31, 37]. The main contribution in internal stresses, σ_i , is coming from the difference in thermal expansion coefficients of metallic alloy and glass,

Fig. 8. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of as-prepared sample 1 (a) and of the same sample with deposited 300 nm thick Cu-layer (b) 300 nm thick Co-layer (c) and 600 nm thick Permalloy layer (d).

Fig. 9. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the same sample 1 with deposited 300 nm thick Co-layer (a) and 600 nm thick Co-layer (b).

Fig. 10. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the same sample 1 with deposited 300 nm thick Cu-layer (a) and 600 nm thick Cu-layer (b).

Fig. 11. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of as-prepared sample 2 (a) and of the same sample with deposited 300 nm thick Cu-layer (b) 300 nm thick Co-layer (c) and 600 nm thick Permalloy layer (d).

giving rise to the largest axial component of internal stresses [30,31,37]. Although such internal stresses of tensor origin are distributed in a complex way inside the metallic nucleus, the circular, σ_ϕ , radial, σ_r , and axial, σ_z , components of such internal stresses can be expressed as [8, 31]:

$$\sigma_\phi = \sigma_r = P = \epsilon E_m k \Delta / \left(\frac{k}{3} + 1 \right) \Delta + 4/3; \sigma_z = P((k+1)\Delta + 2) / (k\Delta + 1) \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta = (1-\rho^2)/\rho^2$, $k = E_g/E_m$, E_m , E_g -metallic alloy and glass Young modulus respectively, $\epsilon = (\alpha_m - \alpha_g)(T_m - T_{room})$, α_m , α_g are thermal expansion coefficients of metallic nucleus and glass, respectively, and T_m , T_{room} are melting and room temperatures. From (4) it is clear, that all the internal stresses components are affected by the ρ -ratio ($\rho = d/D$). Therefore, deposition of the additional layer on the top of glass-coating affects the σ_i -value. As shown in several previous publications [36,38], the presence of such metallic layers on top of the glass-coating gives rise to additional compressive stresses. The compressive nature of the stresses induced by the deposited metallic layers is confirmed by the modification of the hysteresis loops (see Figs. 5 and 6): after the deposition of metallic layers, all low-field hysteresis loops become more rectangular.

Generally, the presence of magnetic layers affects the hysteresis loops in similar way as the non-magnetic Cu-layer: the hysteresis loops become more rectangular (see Figs. 5 and 6). As shown previously [20, 32,33], a decrease in internal stresses (with the highest axial component) after annealing is also reflected by a more rectangular hysteresis loop shape. In this case, an increase in both M_r/M_0 and H_c is generally observed [20,32,33]. In the case of the studied samples, an increase in M_r/M_0 after deposition of magnetic and non-magnetic layers is observed for both samples. However, a slight increase in H_c is observed only for the sample 2, whereas a slight decrease in H_c is observed for the sample 1. This difference can be attributed to different λ_s -values of studied samples: $-3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $-1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for the samples 1 and 2 respectively.

In Co-rich amorphous alloys with vanishing λ_s -value and stress, σ , dependence of λ_s can be relevant. Experimentally observed $\lambda_s(\sigma)$ dependence was described as [39]:

$$\lambda_{s,\sigma} = \lambda_{s,0} - B\sigma \quad (5)$$

Fig. 12. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the same sample 2 with deposited 300 nm thick Co-layer (a) and 600 nm thick Cu-layer (b).

Fig. 13. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the same sample 2 with deposited 300 nm thick Cu-layer (a) and 600 nm thick Cu-layer (b).

where $\lambda_{s,\sigma}$ is the magnetostriction coefficient under stress, $\lambda_{s,0}$ is the zero-stress magnetostriction coefficient and B is a positive coefficient of order 10^{-10} MPa.

An increase in λ_s upon compressive stresses generated by the presence of magnetic layers deposited onto studied Co-rich microwires must be responsible for a decrease in internal stresses and change of the hysteresis loops and H_c -values.

The opposite change observed for very thick (several μm) non-magnetic layers found by Pirota et al. [36] (with loops becoming less rectangular and more inclined) is not seen in our case.

The less noticeable influence of the deposited metallic layers on $\Delta Z/Z_m$ (f) in sample 1 must be explained by much stronger internal stresses in the sample 1. From the detailed analysis of the internal stresses [37] it was deduced that the main contribution to σ_i -value is originated by the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients of the metallic alloy and glass and the σ_i -value is affected by the ρ -ratio ($\rho = d/D$): the lower the ρ -ratio, the higher the internal stresses. For the sample 1 with $d = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $D = 11.9 \mu\text{m}$ $\rho = 0.71$, while in the sample 2 with $d = 19.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $D = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$ $\rho = 0.85$. Considering the maximum σ_i -value, σ_{im} , evaluation depending on ρ -ratio [37], at a fixed glass-coating thickness, the σ_{im} -value for a microwire with $d = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$ is almost 50% larger than a microwire with $d = 19.8 \mu\text{m}$. Accordingly, in sample 1 with a lower ρ -ratio, smaller influence of compressive stresses originated by the deposited metallic layers is expected than in sample 2.

Fig. 14. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the same sample 2 with deposited 300 nm thick Permalloy-layer (a) and 600 nm thick Permalloy-layer (b).

As we have seen before, (see Figs. 5 and 6), the changes induced in the shape of the loops by the magnetic coatings are smaller, likely due to the magnetostatic interactions between the magnetic coating and the magnetic microwire. Evidently, this is affected by the hardness/softness of the magnetic coating (and microwire) and by their relative thickness. Hence, Borza et al. observed a quite marked change in the shape of the loops, increasing strongly the squareness, when a layer of 650 nm of Co or CoPt was deposited on top of a microwire of CoFeSiB [27]. Meanwhile, in the case of quite thick (several μm) electrodeposited Co-Ni layers on top of ultrasoft CoFe-based alloy and Fe-Si-B alloy microwires, the shape of the loop may change and effective bias coupling may occur [38–40].

On the other hand, the hysteresis loops, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies in both samples with non-magnetic and magnetic (Co or Permalloy) layers are rather different. Such difference in magnetic properties and GMI effect must be related to the magnetic properties of the layer deposited on the glass-coating. Thus, such a layer in its remanence state, has non-zero magnetization and hence can create a stray field that can affect both hysteresis loops and GMI behavior of the amorphous soft magnetic nucleus. Such magnetostatic interaction between two magnetic wires with different magnetic properties has been recently experimentally observed in array consisting of magnetically soft Co-rich microwire and magnetically harder Fe-rich microwire [41]. Additionally, the onset of the magnetic bias in bi-phase systems arising from dipolar-like interactions in the amorphous ribbons and wires

prepared by rapid solidification techniques, surrounded by an electroplated layer and the asymmetric $\Delta Z/Z_m$ dependencies in amorphous microwire covered by the electroplated layer have been previously observed and discussed in terms of the magnetostatic coupling with the hard magnetic phase [40,42,43]. Accordingly, the difference in hysteresis loops, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies between the studied microwires with magnetic and non-magnetic layers deposited on the glass-coating must be attributed to either magnetoelastic or magnetostatic coupling between the metallic amorphous magnetically soft nucleus and metallic layers deposited on the glass-coating.

The aforementioned stray field, H_d , is determined by the macroscopic demagnetizing factor, D , of the deposited layer, as given below [41,44]:

$$H_d = D_{co} M \quad (6)$$

where M is the magnetization of the magnetic layer.

The H_d -value and its spatial distribution are affected by applied magnetic field, H , and shape of the layer, which is actually has a form of a tube, magnetic layer thickness and magnetic anisotropy of the deposited magnetic layer. There are only a very few previous publications dealing with the demagnetizing factor of the tubes [45]. In the case of cylinders, there are several experimental and theoretical publications [46–48]. Thus, the two-pole magnetic structure of magnetic wire has been observed at high enough external magnetic field [47,48].

Fig. 15. $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependencies of as-prepared and with deposited layers sample 1 (a) and sample 2 (b).

Table 1

Comparison of $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values and optimal frequencies, f_o , for studied samples.

Sample	$\Delta Z/Z_m$ (%)	f_o , MHz
Sample 1, as-prepared	175	100
Sample 1, 300 nm thick Cu layer	127	50
Sample 1, 600 nm thick Cu layer	142	80
Sample 1, 600 nm thick Py layer	170	100
Sample 1, 300 nm thick Co layer	114	50
Sample 1, 600 nm thick Co layer	115	80
Sample 2, as-prepared	184	150
Sample 2, 300 nm thick Cu layer	200	80
Sample 2, 600 nm thick Cu layer	217	100
Sample 2, 300 nm thick Py layer	198	200
Sample 2, 600 nm thick Py layer	262	100
Sample 2, 300 nm thick Co layer	205	80
Sample 2, 600 nm thick Co layer	283	150

Additionally, the magnetic field component normal to the wire axis is experimentally observed close to the wire ends [47,48]. Accordingly, higher contribution of the stray field produced by the magnetically harder Co layer is expected. On the other hand, when the thickness of the deposited magnetically hard layer is large enough (in order of a few μm), the magnetostatic bias becomes effective to produce shift in hysteresis loops after application of high enough magnetic field [49]. In the present case the thickness of the deposited magnetic layer was an order of magnitude lower. Therefore, as expected from previous studies, the magnetostatic interaction was not strong enough to produced shift in hysteresis loops and in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies [43,49]. However, the presence of the magnetostatic interaction in our case is evidenced by the difference in both hysteresis loops and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies in the samples with the same thickness magnetic and non-magnetic layers. Modelling of magnetic impedance effect [50,51] could be fairly useful to obtain complementary information about the samples. Therefore, we are considering that option for future related works.

4. Conclusion

We report on the tailoring of magnetic properties and the giant magnetoimpedance effect in amorphous Co-rich glass-coated microwires with magnetic and non-magnetic layers deposited onto glass-coating. We studied two Co-rich samples: $\text{Co}_{67}\text{Fe}_{3.85}\text{Ni}_{1.45}\text{B}_{11.5}\text{Si}_{14.5}\text{Mo}_{1.7}$ and $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{1}\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires which present soft magnetic properties and high GMI effect. In such microwires with deposited magnetic and non-magnetic layers, we observed a substantial impact of deposited magnetic and non-magnetic layers on GMI effect and hysteresis loops. The hysteresis loops of both studied microwires with deposited magnetic layers are similar to those observed in microwires with mixed amorphous-crystalline structures with visible hysteresis up to the high magnetic field. Low field hysteresis loops of both samples present systematic change upon deposition of non-magnetic and magnetic layers towards more rectangular hysteresis loops. The GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$ and magnetic field, H , dependences of GMI effect are affected by the magnetic and non-magnetic layers deposited onto glass-coating. In the case of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{1}\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires we substantially improved the GMI effect. The observed experimental dependences are discussed considering both changes in the internal stresses originated by the deposited layers and the magnetostatic interaction between the amorphous ferromagnetic nucleus and the deposited magnetic layer.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

R. López Antón: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J.P. Andrés:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **J.A. González:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **A. García-**

Gómez: Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **V. Zhukova:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **A. Chizhik:** Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **M. Salaheldeen:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **A. Zhukov:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Interest declaration

The authors of the manuscript “*Tuning of magnetic properties and Giant Magnetoimpedance effect in multilayered microwires*” R. López Antón, J. P. Andrés, J. A. González, A. García-Gómez, V. Zhukova, A. Chizhik, M. Salaheldeen and A. Zhukov declare no competing financial or/and non-financial interests.

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